

LABYRINTH SEAL FLUTTER: DEVELOPMENT & VALIDATION OF AN IMPROVED CONTROL VOLUME APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

The seal flutter instability is revisited and explained using a special frame of reference from which the cavity flow becomes steady, allowing an intuitive understanding of the problem. A seal flutter model is then presented building upon the work by Lewis [3], Abbott [4], Phibel [6] and more recently Corral & Vega [8]. The model is extended to account for aerodynamic stiffness, which is shown to produce a destabilizing effect particularly important at resonance conditions. This effect also means careful use of the prescribed vibration method in CFD analyses is required as it may lead to wrong aerodynamic damping predictions. The analytical model is further extended to deal with seals of multiple cavities where cross-cavity coupling arises due to the fin tip leakage being affected by the pressure response from adjacent cavities. It is shown that once these two effects are included in the model, the predictions are significantly improved when compared to CFD and experimental data.

Keywords: seal, flutter, stability, damping, stiffness.

NOMENCLATURE

A : area
 a_c : speed of sound in seal cavity
 C_D : discharge coefficient
 f : frequency
 F : modal force
 h : non-dimensional parameter (eq. A14)
 L : cavity length, axial direction
 H : fin tip clearance
HPS: seal supported from high-pressure side
 i : imaginary number
 k : stiffness coefficient
 Δk_a : aerodynamic stiffness
LPS: seal supported from low-pressure side
 m (\dot{m}): mass (flow rate)
 M : Mach number
 m_ψ : modal mass associated to mode-shape ψ
 ND : nodal diameter
 p : static pressure
 c_p, s_p : pressure coefficients for cosine and sine components

PR : pressure ratio
 q : modal displacement
 Q : non-dimensional mass flow rate
 r : distance from torsion center to pressure center on cavity wall
 R : specific gas constant
 R_c : mean cavity radius
 R_w : radius of inner cavity wall
 s : cavity height, radial direction
 $S = 2\pi R_c L$: surface area
 $St = \omega/\omega_{ac}$: Strouhal number based on ω
 $St_m = \omega_m/\omega_{ac}$: Strouhal number based on ω_m
 T : static temperature
 t : time
 v : flow velocity in tangential direction
 $\hat{v}_c = \gamma \Delta v_c / \bar{a}_c$: non-dimensional flow tangential velocity
 V_{mt} : volume bounded by the seal's material
 V : volume
 x : axial coordinate
 $z = R_c \cdot \theta$: circumferential coordinate
 $\tilde{z} = ND \cdot \theta$: non-dimensional circumferential coordinate

Greek Symbols

α : rotation angle around torsion center
 γ : specific heat ratio
 δ : physical radial displacement (also used as differential operator)
 Δ : operator, difference between a quantity and its mean value
 ε : non-dimensional parameter (eq. A35)
 θ : azimuthal coordinate
 κ : non-dimensional parameter (eq. A35)
 λ : wavelength
 μ : seal-to-air mass ratio
 ρ : density
 ρ_{mt} : density of seal's material
 φ : non-dimensional discharge time based on ω_{ac} (eq. A35)
 ψ : mode-shape
 ω : angular frequency of the vibration
 ω_{ac} : angular acoustic frequency
 ω_m : angular frequency of the structure
 ω_s : wave rotational speed
 $\tilde{\omega} = \omega/\omega_m$: non-dimensional frequency
 Ω : non-dimensional discharge time based on ω (eq. A32)

Super-scripts

- circumferentially averaged (or time-averaged across a period)
- non-dimensional (as in $\Delta p/\bar{p}$, unless specified otherwise)

Sub-scripts

- c* Cavity
- e* Exit (downstream)
- f* Fin tip location
- i* Inlet (upstream)
- m* Mechanical
- n* Cavity numbering (see Figure 7)
- o* Amplitude
- T* Total quantity (e.g. total pressure)
- θ Azimuthal direction
- $0L$ Zero-leakage case

1. INTRODUCTION

Labyrinth seals are critical components in gas turbines used to minimize the flow across cavities operating at different pressures. They consist of a sequence of constrictions and cavities through which the air flow travels. The air accelerates through these constrictions leading to an increase in kinetic energy, which is subsequently dissipated during the expansion into the next inter-fin cavity. The flow through the seal is then reduced by the continuous throttling of the flow between the inter-fin cavities.

Labyrinth seals are known to be susceptible to aeroelastic instabilities due to their dynamic interaction with the leakage flow. This interaction leads to aeroelastic vibrations that can result in seal failure. Seal flutter is a type of instability where the air through the seal provides net positive energy to the structure across a vibration cycle leading to growth in amplitude.

Analytical models to study seal flutter were developed in the 60's and 70's and helped establish a set of stability criteria for design considerations. Alford [1] highlighted the importance of the support side of the seal and found that the tangential component of the air velocity in the inter-fin cavities has an important effect on acoustic resonance frequency. Ehrich [2] developed an analytical model, valid only for zero nodal diameter vibration modes, from which he was able to show the importance of the seal clearance and location of the torsional center. Lewis [3] extended the analytical model to include flow variations in the circumference direction making it valid for any nodal diameter. The analytical model allowed them to support the findings from the experimental tests on a 4-fin labyrinth seal, revealing the importance of the fin clearance distribution on the overall stability. Abbott [4] presented a similar analytical model and introduced the concept of acoustic resonance within the seal inter-fin cavities which is now central to understanding flutter onset. His work highlighted the importance of the seal support side and the ratio between structural and acoustic frequencies, in determining the seal stability. Abbott verified his conclusions from the analytical model with experimental results. And Srinivasan [5] extended Lewis and Abbott's models to include vibration modes on both stator and rotor sides.

More recently, Phibel [6] conducted numerical simulations of seal flutter and compare the results against analytical models of different levels of complexity, obtaining differing levels of

accuracy. Corral & Vega, [8] and [9], developed a model for a single-cavity seal and derived an explicit expression to calculate the work per vibration cycle. This allowed them to define key non-dimensional parameters for seal stability. This model has recently been extended by Corral, Vega & Greco in [10] to deal with stepped seals, Corral, Greco & Vega in [11] to include the more realistic, non-isentropic process in the seal cavities by resolving the energy equation and in [12] to include the effects of the kinetic energy carry-over in straight-through seals. A non-linear version of the analytical model has also been reported in [13] by Corral, Greco & Matabuena, highlighting the importance of non-linear effects when the vibration induces clearance variations comparable to the size of the steady clearances.

This paper extends previous analytical models to include two effects. The first one relates to the influence of the seal aerodynamics on the vibration frequency, characterized by the *aerodynamic stiffness*. Previous analytical models have assumed that the frequency of the vibration is equal to the natural frequency of the structure. This assumption is discussed in Appendix B of reference [8], where Corral & Vega revisited Ehrich's analysis in [2] and concluded that for most cases this is a good assumption. Nonetheless, the authors have found that the aerodynamic stiffness can have a critical influence on the flutter stability of the seal in realistic applications. In some instances, the flutter prediction went from stable to unstable when this effect was included, thus motivating the research of this effect.

The second effect applies specifically to multiple cavity labyrinth seals. Corral & Vega [9] propose to treat each inter-fin cavity in isolation and to sum the contributions from each cavity in terms of work per vibration cycle, to determine the overall seal stability. Instead, this paper shows that the unsteady flow response in one cavity is affected by the unsteady conditions in the adjacent cavities due to their influence on the fin tip leakage flow. A model that accounts for the coupling that arises across the cavities is presented. It is shown that the inclusion of this effect significantly improves the flutter predictions from the model when compared to CFD results and experimental data.

These two effects appear to be implicit in the early analytical models by Abbott [4] and Srinivasan [5]. However, these effects have not been explicitly discussed before nor compared to CFD results or validated by experimental data.

2. A PHYSICAL OVERVIEW OF SEAL FLUTTER

Several papers in the literature, e.g. [5], [8] and [15], provide a thorough derivation of the governing equations that describe the flow during seal vibration but it can be difficult to distill this information into a physical, *engineering* understanding of the seal flutter problem. The primary goal of this section is to help the engineer develop an intuition of the phenomenon. Some simplifying assumptions are made to ease the conceptual description, such as the use of isentropic flow conditions.

Firstly, the case of a *fully sealed cavity* with zero-leakage flow through is considered. After this, the more representative case of a single-cavity labyrinth seal with leakage flow will be addressed. In both cases the cavity is assumed to be stationary (i.e. non-rotating walls) and a vibration mode of certain nodal

diameter (ND) and frequency is imposed on the cavity. The vibration mode is axially characterized by a pivot point or center of torsion (see Figure 4). The static pressure response within the seal cavity is then described and its impact on the work per vibration cycle and thus seal stability is then established. The following discussion will be limited to $ND > 0$.

2.1. Fully sealed cavity (zero-leakage flow)

Consider an annular cavity with a rectangular cross-section as shown in Figure 1. The inner wall of the cavity is assumed to vibrate with a prescribed amplitude and frequency. *Small* displacements with radial component only are considered. The vibration mode is assumed to occur in travelling wave form as viewed from the air frame of reference. Since the cavity is assumed to be stationary, the air frame of reference used in this analysis, is also stationary.

FIGURE 1: VIBRATION MODE IN SEAL CAVITY INNER WALL

The cavity cross-sectional area variation driven by the vibration is described by

$$A_\theta - \bar{A}_\theta = \Delta A_o \cos(ND\theta - \omega t) \quad (1)$$

Where the cross-sectional area is defined by $A_\theta = Ls$ and ω is the frequency of vibration in rad/s. The cavity height, s , varies as a function of time and circumferential position due to the vibration of the inner wall.

The rotational wave speed ω_s , in rad/s, of the vibration travelling wave on the inner wall is given by:

$$\omega_s = \frac{\lambda f}{R_w} = \frac{\omega}{ND} \quad (2)$$

Where λ is the wavelength and f the frequency in Hz, $f = \omega/2\pi$. As a result of the vibration, the air within the cavity responds with air particles vibrating at the same frequency as that prescribed by ω . An unsteady pressure wave then develops in travelling wave form matching the structure, which can be shown to be of the form:

$$p_c - \bar{p}_c = \Delta p_o \cdot \cos(ND\theta - \omega t) \quad (3)$$

The amplitude of the unsteady pressure wave Δp_o is derived in Appendix A and given by equation A37, written here again:

$$\frac{\Delta p_o}{\bar{p}_c} = \gamma \frac{St^2}{(1-St^2)} \frac{\Delta A_o}{A_\theta} \quad (A37)$$

¹ The use of such a frame of reference is limited to $ND > 0$, since equation 2 diverges for $ND = 0$.

Where St is the Strouhal number defined as the ratio of the vibration frequency to the acoustic frequency, $St = \omega/\omega_{ac}$. The phase of p_c with respect to A_θ is defined by the sign of $(1 - St^2)$ from equation A37. For $St < 1$, the unsteady pressure p_c is in-phase with A_θ and for $St > 1$, it is 180° out-of-phase. A discontinuity exists at $St = 1$, corresponding to the acoustic resonance condition.

An alternative, equally valid frame of reference to study the seal cavity flow is that of the vibration travelling wave, see right-hand side of Figure 2. In this frame of reference, the wall vibration wave appears stationary while the air now appears to be rotating in the opposite direction and at the same speed as that of the vibration wave given by equation 2. The resulting air flow stream in the cavity experiences a number of compressions and expansions caused by changes in the cross-sectional area, A_θ , as it travels around the circumference. This situation is analogous to the case of an air flow stream going through a convergent-divergent nozzle. From this frame of reference, a *mean* Mach number of the air flow can be defined by:

$$\bar{M} = \frac{\bar{v}_c}{\sqrt{\gamma R T_c}} \quad (4)$$

With $\bar{v}_c = \omega_s R_w$ and ω_s is given by equation 2¹.

FIGURE 2: FRAME OF REFERENCES

Two flow regimes can then be considered: i) The subsonic case (i.e. $\bar{M} < 1$) for which an increase in cross-sectional area leads to an increase in static pressure and vice-versa. ii) The supersonic case (i.e. $\bar{M} > 1$) for which an increase in the area leads to a reduction in the static pressure and vice-versa. This is illustrated in Figure 3.

From this frame of reference, a stationary pressure wave forms in the cavity and its phase with respect to the cross-sectional area is a function of the mean Mach number. In subsonic conditions, the static pressure variation is in phase with the cross-sectional area variation while in the supersonic case, there is a 180° phase difference. The advantage of using this frame of reference (shown in the right-hand side of Figure 2) is that the flow in the cavity now appears *steady*.

Equation A37 leads to a discontinuity at $St = 1$, which is equivalent to $\bar{M} = 1$ from the frame of reference of vibration wave. Indeed, it is known that at a Mach number close to 1, *small*

area changes results in flow discontinuities. This situation can only be captured by a non-linear version of equation A37.

FIGURE 3: STATIC PRESSURE VARIATIONS AS A FUNCTION OF FLOW REGIME

The pressure response in the cavity due to the vibration generates a force back onto the structure proportional to the imposed vibration amplitude:

$$\delta F_{air} = \Delta p_0 L R_c \delta \theta \quad (5)$$

The physical radial displacement of the inner wall is related to the variation of the cross-sectional area, $\Delta A_\theta = L \Delta s$, where $\Delta s = s - \bar{s}$. Substituting equation A37 into 5 we get:

$$\delta F_{air} = - \left(\gamma \frac{St^2}{(St^2-1)} \frac{L \cdot R_c \cdot \delta \theta}{\bar{s}} \bar{p}_c \right) \Delta s_\theta \quad (6)$$

With the term in the bracket representing an aerodynamic stiffness, Δk_a . For $St < 1$ the pressure increases as A_θ increases leading to a force in the same direction as the motion, which can be expressed as a negative stiffness. Therefore, the system frequency will tend to be lower than the mechanical frequency. For the case of $St > 1$ the converse is true, resulting in a positive stiffness leading to a system frequency which is higher than the mechanical frequency. In both cases the system frequency is *pushed away* from the natural frequency of the structure, somewhat similar to the behavior of a vibration absorber with the air acting as a second mass, although in the seal system the additional stiffness is a function of frequency. Equation 6 shows that the pressure force amplitude is largest near $St = 1$, where the aerodynamic stiffness effect is greatest. In fact, the total stiffness of the system is given by:

$$k_T(\omega) = k_m + \Delta k_a(\omega) \quad (7)$$

Where k_m is the stiffness of the structure and Δk_a (term in brackets in equation 6) depends on St and therefore on ω . Equation 7 can be solved for ω , the vibration frequency of the system. This will be presented in section 3.1.

Moreover, the net work per vibration cycle (and thus aerodynamic damping) is zero because the pressure and cross-sectional area (thus displacement) are either in-phase or 180° out-of-phase. The seal is then neutrally stable.

Clearly the idealized case with zero-leakage flow leads only to an additional aerodynamic stiffness, with no instability present. The next section examines the effect of adding the leakage flow to the cavity. It will be shown that this leads to non-zero aerodynamic damping.

2.2. Case 2: Single Cavity with leakage

A similar description as provided in section 2.1 is presented here now considering leakage flow through the cavity, see Figure 4. The frame of reference used here rotates at the speed of the vibration travelling wave as shown in the right-hand side of Figure 2. Appendix A provides a derivation of the static pressure response using this frame of reference, demonstrating that the result is equivalent to that obtained by Corral & Vega [8].

Viewed from this frame of reference, both the flow within the cavity and the fin tip leakage flow appears in steady state. The local leakage flow rate may be different between upstream and downstream fins, thus the local net leakage flow rate into the cavity may be positive or negative. The variation of the net leakage flow rate around the circumference causes the phase between the static pressure wave and the cavity cross-sectional area wave to change away from the ideal, zero-leakage case considered in section 2.1. This is illustrated in Figure 5. The phase shift can be positive or negative and will lead to either positive or negative work input per vibration cycle, ultimately determining the stability of the seal.

FIGURE 4: SINGLE CAVITY SEAL WITH LEAKAGE

Consider the continuity and mass-momentum (linearized) equations for this case, derived in Appendix A:

$$\rho_{c,2} v_{c,2} A_{\theta,2} = \rho_{c,1} v_{c,1} A_{\theta,1} + \delta \dot{m} \quad (A1)$$

$$\frac{\partial p_c}{\partial \theta} A_\theta = -\bar{m}_\theta \frac{\partial v_c}{\partial \theta} \quad (A25)$$

Where the sub-scripts 1 and 2 represent two circumferential positions separated by a distance $\delta \theta$ (see Figure 4) and $\delta \dot{m} = \dot{m}_{fi} - \dot{m}_{fe}$ represents the net leakage flow rate into the cavity. The continuity equation shows that the circumferential velocity gradient $v_{c,2} - v_{c,1}$ is not only a function of the cross-sectional area gradient, $A_{\theta,2} - A_{\theta,1}$, (as in the zero-leakage case) but also a function of $\delta \dot{m}$. And, from equation A25, so is the circumferential static pressure gradient.

The net leakage flow rate $\delta \dot{m}$ is a function of the local fin tip flow which, in turn, is a function of the pressure ratio, the fin tip clearance and the feed pressure and temperature (see equation A3), all of which can vary around the circumference. However, the dominant factor in setting the fin tip leakage flow rate is its clearance. This is why the support location of the seal (i.e. center of torsion) plays a major role in determining the flutter stability: Seals supported from the low-pressure side (LPS) will tend to exhibit a net leakage flow rate ($\delta \dot{m}$) in-phase with the cross-sectional area (i.e. $\delta \dot{m} > 0$, when $\Delta A_\theta > 0$, etc). While seals

supported from the high-pressure side (HPS) will tend to have a net leakage flow rate ($\delta\dot{m}$) that is 180° out of phase relative to the cross-sectional area (i.e. $\delta\dot{m} > 0$, when $\Delta A_\theta < 0$, etc).

A qualitative explanation to the trends presented in Figure 5 is provided next. For simplicity, uniform mean fin clearances are assumed. It should be noted that in this linear analysis the pressure response is expected to be of the same wave form (same *ND*) as the cross-sectional area wave, with its amplitude and phase constrained by the continuity and mass-momentum equations (A1 and A25). Consider the LPS case at low mean Mach number conditions (equivalent to $St \ll 1$). The flow may be treated as incompressible¹, since the Mach number is much lower than 1 (i.e. $\rho_{c,1} = \rho_{c,2} = \rho_c$). Equation A1 becomes:

$$v_{c,2}A_{\theta,2} = v_{c,1}A_{\theta,1} + \frac{\delta\dot{m}}{\rho_c} \quad (8)$$

Three different local conditions around the circumference, labeled A, B and C in the top plot of Figure 5, are considered:

Condition A: The flow is going through a convergent section ($A_{\theta,2} < A_{\theta,1}$) with positive net leakage flow (i.e. $A_{\theta,1}$ and $A_{\theta,2} > \bar{A}_\theta$, so that $\delta\dot{m} > 0$). Equation 8 requires an increase in tangential velocity $v_{c,2} > v_{c,1}$ greater than for the zero-leakage case ($\delta\dot{m} = 0$), which leads to a larger static pressure drop, as required by equation A25.

Condition B: The flow is going through a convergent section ($A_{\theta,2} < A_{\theta,1}$) but in this case the upstream and downstream fin gap areas are equal since $(A_{\theta,2} + A_{\theta,1})/2 = \bar{A}_\theta$. In this simplified analysis where the leakage is assumed to be only proportional to the fin gap area, the local net leakage flow at B is then zero, $\delta\dot{m} = 0$. Equation 8 requires that the increase in tangential velocity is the same as in the zero-leakage case and therefore the static pressure drop is locally unchanged.

Condition C: The flow is going through a convergent section ($A_{\theta,2} < A_{\theta,1}$) with negative net leakage flow (i.e. $A_{\theta,1}$ and $A_{\theta,2} < \bar{A}_\theta$, so that $\delta\dot{m} < 0$). Equation 8 requires an increase in tangential velocity $v_{c,2} > v_{c,1}$ lower than for the zero-leakage case ($\delta\dot{m} = 0$), which leads to a smaller static pressure drop, as required by equation A25.

These results are summarized in the red box shown in the top plot of Figure 5. The changes to the pressure gradient at conditions A and C can only be satisfied by a *shift* to the left in the pressure wave relative to the zero-leakage case. This phase shift gives rise to a non-zero aerodynamic damping situation. In fact, since the pressure wave leads the cross-sectional area for the LPS seal case with $St < 1$, it can be shown that the damping is negative, and the seal is unstable. Moreover, the pressure gradient at condition B is required to remain unchanged, which could not happen with a simple phase shift – an increase in the pressure amplitude is also required, as shown in Figure 5. The analogous assessment can be done in the divergent section leading to consistent phase and amplitude requirements. In fact, in Appendix A it is shown that, under the assumption that the

¹ The assumption of incompressible flow is convenient, but a similar analysis can be applied even when density changes are considered, leading to the same conclusions.

leakage flow is only proportional to the fin gap area, the pressure wave is the result of a superposition of the zero-leakage case (denoted by the subscript 0L in Figure 5) and a pressure wave that is +/-90° out of phase, which is a function of the net leakage flow distribution, $\delta\dot{m}$ (see equations A38 and A39).

Other cases (e.g. HPS & $St < 1$, LPS & $St > 1$ and, HPS & $St > 1$) can be assessed similarly. The results lead to the well-known Abbott's criteria, summarized in Table 1 and reflected in Figure 5 in wave form.

	$St < 1$	$St > 1$
LPS	Unstable	Stable
HPS	Stable	Unstable

TABLE 1: ABBOTT'S CRITERIA² [4]

It is emphasized that the analysis presented here has assumed that the leakage is only proportional to the fin gap area. In reality, the leakage is also a function of the pressure ratio and feed conditions. An increase in the fin gap area will tend to reduce the fin pressure ratio thus offsetting the increase in the leakage flow rate (and vice-versa). This, in turn, will affect the local net leakage flow rate, depending on the mean pressure ratio of the cavity fins, which will influence the trends presented in Figure 5. For the mean uniform clearance case, the pressure ratio influence can be shown to provide a stabilizing effect (this is why the *zero-damping* point lies at $St < 1$ for LPS seals and at $St > 1$ for HPS seals, as shown in Figure 11).

FIGURE 5: EFFECT OF THE LEAKAGE FLOW ON THE STATIC PRESSURE WAVE

² In [4], Abbot presents actual characteristics typical of LPS and HPS seals and shows that the boundary between stable/unstable regions does not lie exactly at $St = 1$. Therefore, the criteria shown should be taken as a rule of thumb.

The results in Figure 5 can be plotted in a Δp_c versus ΔA_θ diagram, as shown in Figure 6. The zero-leakage case described in section 3, with both Δp_c and ΔA_θ either in phase or 180° out of phase, is represented by the diagonal straight lines. The phase shift in Δp_c relative to ΔA_θ caused by the introduction of the leakage flow transforms the straight lines into ellipses. The sense of direction in which the ellipse is tracked and the quadrants in which it sits is a function of whether the seal is LPS or HPS and whether St is above or below 1. This is summarized in Figure 6.

The cases discussed in sections 2.1 and 2.2 assumed non-rotating seals. The extension to rotating seals is simple if a bulk swirl velocity is defined. The analysis in the rotating frame of the vibration travelling wave remains valid, with the exception that the mean Mach number of the flow is now affected by the mean swirl velocity induced by the rotor (equivalent to the Doppler shift in frequency if the analysis is conducted in the air frame of reference [8]).

FIGURE 6: PRESSURE VERSUS CROSS-SECTIONAL AREA A_θ VARIATIONS

3. EXTENSIONS TO THE SEAL FLUTTER MODEL

The seal flutter model presented here builds upon the work by Abbott [4], Srinivasan [5], Phibel [6] and Corral & Vega [8]. The approach used here follows that described in [8] and extended in [10], [11] and [12]. In this approach a certain vibration mode of interest is prescribed on the seal structure. The equations of mass, mass-momentum and energy conservation are applied and the flow in the seal inter-fin cavities is then resolved. The static pressure response in the cavity is then determined, from which the work per vibration cycle done by the air on the structure is then calculated. The seal aerodynamic damping is obtained from the work per vibration cycle. The *pivot point* concept may be used to characterize the seal vibration mode-shape, although actual mode-shape data from a Finite Element Model (FEM) solution of the structure is preferred.

The first extension to the flutter model accounts for *aerodynamic stiffness*, which represents the influence of the air

¹ Unless the fin tip flow is choked, in which case the downstream pressure does not affect the fin tip flow rate.

on the frequency of vibration. This effect was already introduced in section 2.1. Section 3.1 provides the mathematical formulation to deal with the more general case of a labyrinth seal.

The second effect is concerned with seals of multiple inter-fin cavities. Here, it is acknowledged that the flow over the fin tip is affected, in general¹, by the pressure response in the upstream and downstream cavities caused by the seal vibration. Consequently, the pressure response in one cavity of the seal is influenced by the pressure responses in the adjacent cavities, upstream and downstream. This leads to a coupling across the cavities. The resultant equations are then coupled, and a system of equations needs to be resolved. The formulation to account for this effect is presented in section 3.2.

In what follows, the simplest form of the analytical model is used, consistent with the formulation presented in Appendix A for the single-cavity seal case. In particular, isentropic flow conditions during seal vibration are assumed. Despite these simplifications, it is highlighted that the formulation described in sections 3.1 and 3.2 can be accommodated in more sophisticated models such as those that include the energy equation (e.g. [11] and [15]) or in non-linear versions of the model, e.g. [13].

The incorporation of these extensions adds some complexity to the seal flutter model. However, the increased computation cost is negligible compared to more expensive methods such as CFD. Moreover, these extensions have been found to improve the results significantly making them comparable to those obtained with CFD or experimentally.

3.1. Aerodynamic Stiffness

When a vibration mode is imposed on the seal, the unsteady pressure response in the seal can affect the frequency of the vibration. This is because the aerodynamic response can have a non-zero stiffness contribution (positive or negative) as was already introduced in 2.1.

Consider a particular inter-fin cavity of a non-rotating seal and let ψ represent the mode-shape of a vibration mode of interest with associated nodal diameter ND and with radial component only. ψ is assumed to be in travelling wave form described from the stationary frame of reference as:

$$\psi = \psi_o(x) \cos(ND \cdot \theta - \omega t) \quad (9)$$

The physical displacement, δ , is prescribed and given by:

$$\delta = \delta_o(x) \cos(ND \cdot \theta - \omega t) \quad (10)$$

The mode-shape is scaled² so that:

$$\psi_o(x) = \frac{\delta_o(x)}{\hat{\delta}_{o,seal}} \quad (11)$$

Where $\hat{\delta}_{o,seal}$ is a reference displacement taken here as the mean displacement amplitude across the seal. Therefore ψ is non-dimensional. The modal displacement is then:

$$q = \frac{\delta}{\psi} = \hat{\delta}_{o,seal} \quad (12)$$

² This choice of scaling the mode-shape is opted here to make the modal mass m_ψ explicit in the equations, with units of mass. However, a mass-normalized mode-shape can be a more convenient way to apply the formulation.

Consider one inter-fin cavity of the seal. The prescribed displacement will produce a static pressure response within the cavity, of the form:

$$\Delta p_c = {}_c p \cdot \cos(ND \cdot \theta - \omega t) + {}_s p \cdot \sin(ND \cdot \theta - \omega t) \quad (13)$$

And the modal force contribution from the cavity is:

$$F = \int_S \Delta p_{st} \psi ds = \frac{{}_c p \mathbb{S} \hat{\delta}_o}{2 \hat{\delta}_{o,seal}} \quad (14)$$

Where $\mathbb{S} = 2\pi R_c L$ and $\hat{\delta}_o$ is the mean displacement over the cavity axial length, L . The modal force for a seal of N cavities is the sum of the modal forces from each cavity:

$$F_{seal} = \sum_{n=1}^N F_n = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{({}_c p \mathbb{S} \hat{\delta}_o)_n}{2 \hat{\delta}_{o,seal}} \quad (15)$$

The aerodynamic stiffness is given by:

$$\Delta k_a = -\frac{F_{seal}}{q_{seal}} = -\frac{F_{seal}}{\hat{\delta}_{o,seal}} \quad (16)$$

The total stiffness, mechanical plus aerodynamic, is given by question 7, $k_T = k_m + \Delta k_a$. Due to Δk_a the seal vibration frequency is not coincident with the natural frequency of the structure. Δk_a can be positive or negative depending on the phase of the pressure and displacement waves, as discussed in section 2.1. The seal vibration frequency is given by:

$$\omega^2 = \frac{k_T}{m_\psi} \quad (17)$$

Where m_ψ is the modal mass associated to the mode-shape defined by equations 9 and 11. Therefore:

$$\omega^2 = \omega_m^2 + \frac{\Delta k_a}{m_\psi} = \omega_m^2 - \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{(\hat{\delta}_o {}_c p \mathbb{S})_n}{2 m_\psi \hat{\delta}_{o,seal}} \quad (18)$$

Where ${}_c p$ is also a function of ω , as shown in Appendix A. Equation 18 can be used to determine ω . In general, this equation cannot be resolved explicitly for ω and a numerical method is required. The vibration frequency that is obtained from equation 18 is different to the natural frequency of the structure and this has an implication on the seal stability, since the aerodynamic damping of the seal depends on the vibration frequency. In fact, in section 4.1 it will be shown that the frequency change relative to the natural frequency is greatest near the stability boundary and that it tends to be destabilizing.

Equation 18 is now presented in non-dimensional form. Without loss of generality, consider a single-cavity seal. In this case $\hat{\delta}_o = \hat{\delta}_{o,seal}$ and Equation 18 can be written as:

$$\tilde{\omega}^2 = 1 - \frac{\Delta k_a}{St_m^2} c\tilde{p} \quad (19)$$

Where $\tilde{\omega} = \frac{\omega}{\omega_m}$, $St_m = \frac{\omega_m}{\omega_{ac}}$, $c\tilde{p} = \frac{{}_c p}{\bar{p}_c}$ and the non-dimensional aerodynamic stiffness is defined as:

$$\tilde{\Delta k}_a = \frac{\mathbb{S}}{2 m_\psi \hat{\delta}_o \omega_{ac}^2} \bar{p}_c \quad (20)$$

The modal mass may be estimated as:

$$m_\psi = \int_V \rho_{mt} |\psi|^2 dV_{mt} \approx \int_0^{2\pi} \rho_{mt} A_{mt} |\hat{\psi}|^2 R_c d\theta = \frac{m_{seal}}{2} \quad (21)$$

Where ρ_{mt} is the seal's material density (assumed uniform), V_{mt} and A_{mt} are the volume and area bounded by the material of the seal, respectively. And $m_{seal} = \rho_{mt} V_{mt}$. $\hat{\psi}$ is the mean mode-shape over the cavity axial length, L

Since $\bar{a}_c^2 = \gamma \frac{\bar{p}_c}{\bar{\rho}_c}$, $\omega_{ac} = \frac{\bar{a}_c ND}{R_c}$, $\bar{V}_c = \mathbb{S} \cdot \bar{s}$, $\lambda = \frac{2\pi R_c}{ND}$ then:

$$\tilde{\Delta k}_a = \frac{1}{4\pi^2 \gamma} \left(\frac{1}{\mu}\right) \left(\frac{\lambda}{\bar{s}}\right)^2 \left(\frac{\bar{s}}{\hat{\delta}_o}\right) \quad (22)$$

Where the mass ratio μ is defined as $\mu = \frac{m_{seal}}{m_{air}}$ and $m_{air} = \bar{V}_c \cdot \bar{\rho}_c$. Equation A33, from Appendix A, provides an expression for ${}_c \tilde{p}$ for the single-cavity seal case:

$${}_c \tilde{p} = \frac{h\varepsilon - \varphi^2 St_m^2 \tilde{\omega}^2 \kappa \left(1 - \frac{1}{St_m^2 \tilde{\omega}^2}\right)}{h^2 + \varphi^2 St_m^2 \tilde{\omega}^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{St_m^2 \tilde{\omega}^2}\right)^2} \quad (A33)$$

Where ε , κ , φ , St_m and $\tilde{\omega}$ are defined by equation A35 and h is defined by A14. Note that $\hat{\delta}_o = \tilde{A}_o \bar{s}$ where $\tilde{A}_o = \frac{\Delta A_o}{A_\theta} = \frac{L \hat{\delta}_o}{L \bar{s}}$.

Thus equation 22 simplifies to:

$$\tilde{\Delta k}_a = \frac{1}{4\pi^2 \kappa} \left(\frac{1}{\mu}\right) \left(\frac{\lambda}{\bar{s}}\right)^2 \quad (23)$$

Equations 22 and 23 show that the aerodynamic stiffness scales proportional to $\left(\frac{\lambda}{\bar{s}}\right)^2$ and inversely proportional to μ .

Combining equations 19 and A33 leads to a 3rd order polynomial the roots of which define $\tilde{\omega}^2$:

$$\varphi^2 St_m^4 \tilde{\omega}^6 + [h^2 St_m^2 + \varphi^2 - \varphi^2 (1 + St_m^2) - \kappa \varphi^2 St_m^2 \tilde{\Delta k}_a] \tilde{\omega}^4 + [\varphi^2 (1 + St_m^2)^2 - St_m^2 (h^2 + \varphi^2 St_m^2) + (\varepsilon h + \kappa \varphi^2) \tilde{\Delta k}_a] \tilde{\omega}^2 - \varphi^2 = 0 \quad (24)$$

For most gas turbine applications, the polynomial of equation 24 has a single, real root. However, for certain cases such as where the seal-to-air mass ratio is *small*, the polynomial can have three real roots - these cases will not be discussed in this paper, as they have limited relevance. Typical trends obtained with equation 24 for the single-cavity seal case are presented in section 4.1.

It should be noted that equation 24 has been obtained after linearizing the flow conservation equations. It has been found that the computed frequency shift using the linear formulation can deviate from the more correct, non-linear formulation such as that in [13]. This is because the linearization of the conservation equations does not correctly model the resonance condition, especially for cases where seal clearances are *small* and the in-phase pressure coefficient ${}_c p$ becomes large (in fact, for the zero-leakage case introduced in section 2.2 and described by equation A37, the pressure amplitude diverges at resonance condition, which is not physically possible). The error incurred with the linear flow flutter model can, therefore, impact the predicted aerodynamic damping near resonance conditions.

3.2. Inter-fin cavity coupling

The leakage flow over the fin tip is, in general, a function of both the feed conditions (pressure and temperature) and the pressure ratio across it. If the fin tip flow is choked, then the downstream pressure does not affect the flow rate. As a result, during seal vibration, the pressure response in one cavity is affected, in general, by the pressure response in the adjacent cavities, upstream and downstream. This effect is accounted for in the mass conservation equation through the leakage mass flux terms.

Consider a seal with multiple cavities as shown in Figure 7. For one of the cavities, with index n and surrounded by the upstream fin n and downstream fin $n+1$, the mass conservation equation applied in the frame of reference of the vibration travelling wave is given in Appendix A, equation A1:

$$\Delta \dot{m}_\theta = \dot{m}_{f,n} - \dot{m}_{f,n+1} \quad (\text{A1})$$

FIGURE 7: MULTIPLE-CAVITY SEAL WITH CAVITY AND FIN INDEXING SHOWN

Where $\Delta \dot{m}_\theta = \dot{m}_2 - \dot{m}_1$, with 1 and 2 denoting two circumferential positions separated by $\delta\theta$, see Figure 14. The fin tip mass flow rates are represented by $\dot{m}_{f,n}$ and $\dot{m}_{f,n+1}$, for upstream and downstream fins respectively. The mass flow rate through fin n is given by:

$$\dot{m}_{f,n} = \frac{p_{c,n-1} C_{Dn} A_{f,n}}{\sqrt{T_{c,n-1}}} Q_n(M_n) = f(p_{c,n-1}, T_{c,n-1} C_{Dn}, A_{f,n}, Q_n(M_n)) \quad (\text{25})$$

Where the fin tip Mach number M_n is a function of the pressure ratio and given by:

$$M_n = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma-1} \left(\left(\frac{p_{c,n-1}}{p_{c,n}} \right)^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}} - 1 \right)}, \quad \text{if } \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma-1} \left(\left(\frac{p_{c,n-1}}{p_{c,n}} \right)^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}} - 1 \right)} < 1$$

$$M_n = 1, \quad \text{if } \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma-1} \left(\left(\frac{p_{c,n-1}}{p_{c,n}} \right)^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}} - 1 \right)} \geq 1 \quad (\text{26})$$

Equations 25 and 26 define the dependency of the leakage flow rate through fin n with its upstream pressure, $P_{c,n-1}$, and downstream pressure $P_{c,n}$. Equation 25 can be linearized as follows:

$$\frac{\Delta \dot{m}_{f,n}}{\bar{\dot{m}}_f} = \frac{\dot{m}_{f,n} - \bar{\dot{m}}_f}{\bar{\dot{m}}_f} \approx \frac{\partial \dot{m}_{f,n}}{\partial p_{c,n-1}} \frac{\Delta p_{c,n-1}}{\bar{\dot{m}}_f} + \frac{\partial \dot{m}_{f,n}}{\partial T_{c,n-1}} \frac{\Delta T_{c,n-1}}{\bar{\dot{m}}_f} + \frac{\partial \dot{m}_{f,n}}{\partial C_{Dn}} \frac{\Delta C_{Dn}}{\bar{\dot{m}}_f} + \frac{\partial \dot{m}_{f,n}}{\partial A_{f,n}} \frac{\Delta A_{f,n}}{\bar{\dot{m}}_f} + \frac{\partial \dot{m}_{f,n}}{\partial Q_n} \frac{\Delta Q_n}{\bar{\dot{m}}_f} + \frac{\partial \dot{m}_{f,n}}{\partial PR_n} \frac{\Delta PR_n}{\bar{\dot{m}}_f} \quad (\text{27})$$

Where $\bar{\dot{m}}_f$ is the mean leakage flow. Expressing each of the terms in the right-hand side of equation 27 as a function of the cavity pressure (similar to the procedure presented in Appendix A) leads to:

$$\frac{\Delta \dot{m}_{f,n}}{\bar{\dot{m}}_f} = \left(\frac{\gamma+1}{2\gamma} + g_n \right) \tilde{p}_{c,n-1} - g_n \tilde{p}_{c,n} + \tilde{H}_n \quad (\text{28})$$

Where:

$$\tilde{p}_{c,n} = \frac{\Delta p_{c,n}}{\bar{p}_{c,n}} \quad (\text{29})$$

$$\tilde{H}_n = \frac{\Delta H_n}{\bar{H}_n} \quad (\text{30})$$

$$g_n = \frac{Q_n'}{Q_n} \bar{PR}_n = f(\bar{PR}_n) \quad (\text{31})$$

And $Q_n' = \frac{\partial Q_n}{\partial PR_n}$, evaluated at the pressure ratio \bar{PR}_n .

Therefore, equation A1 becomes:

$$\Delta \dot{m}_\theta = \left(\frac{\gamma+1}{2\gamma} + g_n \right) \tilde{p}_{c,n-1} - \left(\frac{\gamma+1}{2\gamma} + g_n + g_{n+1} \right) \tilde{p}_{c,n} + g_{n+1} \tilde{p}_{c,n+1} + \tilde{H}_n - \tilde{H}_{n+1} \quad (\text{32})$$

The terms in bold in equation 32 couple the pressure in cavity n ($\tilde{p}_{c,n}$) with pressures in the adjacent cavities ($\tilde{p}_{c,n-1}$ and $\tilde{p}_{c,n+1}$). The rest of the terms in the mass conservation and mass-momentum equations remain the same as those for the single-cavity seal case presented in Appendix A.

The resulting equations accept a solution of the form, in complex notation:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{p}_{c,n} &= p_n e^{i(ND\theta)} \\ \tilde{p}_{c,n-1} &= p_{n-1} e^{i(ND\theta)} \\ \tilde{p}_{c,n+1} &= p_{n+1} e^{i(ND\theta)} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{33})$$

Where the coefficients p_n , p_{n-1} and p_{n+1} are complex numbers. The solution form in equations 33 is formulated in a rotating frame of reference coincident with the vibration travelling wave (as defined by the right-hand side of Figure 2) and it shows that the pressure waves do not have a temporal dependency. This is due to the frame of reference used, which leads to stationary pressure waves in the cavities, as is the case for the single-cavity seal presented in Appendix A. Moreover, equations 33 suggest that the pressure waves across the seal cavities all have the same wavelength matching the vibration but different amplitudes and phases determined by the complex coefficients p_n . It is noted that from the air frame of reference (of one of the cavities), the pressure waves all travel at the same rotation speed equal to the vibration travelling wave.

When the solution given by equations 33 is used in the mass conservation and the mass-momentum equations, a pair of algebraic equations for each cavity are obtained (each corresponding to real and imaginary components, respectively). These coupled, algebraic equations can be written in matrix form resulting in a banded matrix, which can be efficiently inverted using numerical methods and the coefficients p_n (real and imaginary parts) be determined.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To demonstrate the validity of the extensions to the flutter model discussed in section 3, results from CFD and experimental data published in the literature have been used for comparison.

The CFD cases used here are reported in [7] and [14] and represent the case of the rotating seal tested by Kawasaki Heavy Industries Co. Ltd (KHI) in [7]. Experimentally this seal was shown to flutter in $ND = 2$ above a certain pressure ratio that is a function of the rotational speed of the rig. References [7] and [14] assessed the stability of the seal in CFD for several NDs at a condition in which the seal fluttered experimentally, namely $PR = 1.4$, rotor tangential velocity of $36.7m/s$. Steady-state data obtained from an in-house CFD code has been used to provide inputs to the seal flutter model.

Figure 8 reproduces the aerodynamic damping predictions from [7] and [14]. As discussed in [14], the damping values of the low NDs in this seal ($ND = 1$ mainly) are influenced by the acoustic response in the relatively large upstream and downstream cavities around the seal. Reference [14] also reports CFD results for the seal only, excluding the contribution from the adjacent cavities and this is shown with the red curve. Since the flutter model presented in this paper is focused on the damping contributions from the inter-fin cavities, the *Seal Only* result is a better, fairer comparison. The results obtained from the fully featured flutter model of this paper is represented by the blue curve. There is a very good agreement with the CFD result (*Seal Only*). Also shown are the results when the extensions described in section 3 are excluded from the model. For this seal, the effect of the aerodynamic stiffness is negligible (the blue and green curves lie on top of each other). However, it is observed that the inter-fin cavity coupling effect described in section 3.2 has an important impact on the predictions (compare *Uncoupled NoAeroStiff* against *Coupled NoAeroStiff* or *Fully Featured*) and once it is included in the model the results match the CFD data very well.

FIGURE 8: SEAL TESTED BY KHI IN [7]. COMPARISON AGAINST CFD RESULTS REPORTED IN [7] AND [14]

Experimental damping results have been reported from the ARIAS rig testing campaign in [16] and these have been used for validation of the flutter model. Reference [16] reports results for a 4-fin seal supported from the high-pressure side (HPS) and from the low-pressure side (LPS), for which the damping was characterized against seal pressure ratio, using a piezoelectric

excitation system. Only nodal diameter 2 was excited during this test. Both standing wave and travelling wave excitations were conducted.

Figure 9 and Figure 10 reproduce the experimental results (shown as “Exp”) from this rig [16]. The red curve corresponds to damping measurements performed with excitations of the seal in standing wave form while the black, dotted curve corresponds to the travelling wave excitations. Since this is a static seal case, both excitation forms are expected to produce the same behavior, which was confirmed by these results. The figures also show the predictions obtained with the fully featured flutter model. The agreement with the experimental results is excellent.

Figure 9 and Figure 10 also show results if one was to exclude the extensions to the model presented in section 3. The effect of the aerodynamic stiffness was found to be small for this case (compared the *fully featured* and *Coupled NoAeroStiff* curves). On the other hand, the effect of the inter-fin cavity coupling is shown to have a significant impact on the predictions, particularly for the LPS case (compare *fully featured* and *Uncoupled NoAeroStiff*). The predicted trends are much improved with the inclusion of this effect and the pressure ratio at which the LPS case flutters experimentally is now correctly captured. If the cavity coupling effect is excluded, the predicted pressure ratio at which the seal flutters is much higher than measured experimentally, above 1.2 (not shown in Figure 10).

FIGURE 9: COMPARISON AGAINST ARIAS RIG TEST DATA – HIGH-PRESSURE SUPPORTED (HPS) SEAL, 0.7MM CLEARANCE

FIGURE 10: COMPARISON AGAINST ARIAS RIG TEST DATA – LOW-PRESSURE SUPPORTED (LPS) SEAL, 0.7MM CLEARANCE

4.1. Aerodynamic Stiffness Characterization

The cases presented in Figure 8, Figure 9 and Figure 10 were shown not to be sensitive to the aerodynamic stiffness effects. For the KHI rig case, this is because the aerodynamic forcing experienced by the seal near resonance conditions is not significant to influence the seal vibration frequency. On the other hand, for the ARIAS rig seal (both HPS and LPS configurations), the conditions are far away from the acoustic resonance of the inter-fin cavities and the seal clearances were relatively large. Therefore, the aerodynamic forcing levels generated in the cavities are relatively small at the conditions tested.

Nonetheless, the authors have encountered relevant cases in which the aerodynamic stiffness effects has been significant, particularly for seals running with *small* clearances and operating near resonance conditions. In some applications a frequency shift as large as 10% to 15% has been seen due to the aerodynamic stiffness effect, taking the seal from being stable (if no account for it is made) to becoming unstable.

This section presents trends obtained with the single-cavity seal case presented in Appendix A. Both HPS and LPS types are discussed. Figure 11 shows the aerodynamic stiffness and work per vibration cycle plotted against St . The aerodynamic stiffness trends can be explained qualitatively by the results presented in section 2.1. For $St \ll 1$, the aerodynamic stiffness is negative for both LPS and HPS cases, which corresponds to conditions where the pressure force wave is largely in-phase with the cross-sectional area wave during the vibration. For $St \gg 1$, the aerodynamic stiffness is positive since the pressure force and cross-sectional area waves tend to be 180° out-of-phase. The effect of the leakage flow means that the *zero-stiffness* point sits at $St > 1$ for the LPS case ($\varepsilon > 0$) and at $St < 1$ for the HPS case ($\varepsilon < 0$), and is determined by imposing $Re[\hat{p}_o] = 0$ in equation A33:

$$St^2_{0_stiff} = 1 + \frac{h\varepsilon}{\kappa\phi^2} \quad (34)$$

Moreover, for the LPS case the lowest aerodynamic stiffness point sits slightly below $St = 1$ and close to the zero-work-per-cycle point. While for the HPS the largest aerodynamic stiffness point sits slightly above $St = 1$. In both cases, this will lead to a frequency shift that will move the points towards the positive work per vibration cycle (i.e. negative damping) region and therefore result in a loss in flutter stability, as illustrated by the red arrow in the plots.

FIGURE 11: AERODYNAMIC STIFFNESS AND WORK PER VIBRATION CYCLE AS A FUNCTION OF St FOR LPS AND HPS SEALS

Figure 12 shows the frequency ratio ($\tilde{\omega} = \frac{\omega}{\omega_m}$) as a function of St_m , where $St = St_m \tilde{\omega}$. These results were obtained after resolving equation 24. The largest absolute frequency shift occurs near $St_m = 1$ and is negative for the LPS case and positive for the HPS case. The point at which the frequency ratio is 1 is described by equation 34.

FIGURE 12: FREQUENCY RATIO ($\tilde{\omega}$) AS A FUNCTION OF St FOR LPS & HPS SEALS

The frequency change shown in Figure 12 causes a shift in the work per vibration cycle plot presented in Figure 11. This is shown in Figure 13. The curves with the label $\Delta k_a = 0$ correspond to the case where the aerodynamic stiffness is neglected and are the same as the work per vibration cycle curves shown in Figure 11. The curve with the label $\Delta k_a \neq 0$ includes the aerodynamic stiffness effect on the vibration frequency.

For both HPS and LPS seals the aerodynamic stiffness effect tends to destabilize the seal, particularly at conditions near $St_m = 1$, as indicated by the red arrows, and the region of positive work per vibration cycle (i.e. negative damping) is extended over a wider range of St_m .

FIGURE 13: WORK PER VIBRATION CYCLE AS A FUNCTION OF St_m FOR LPS AND HPS SEALS

The results presented in this section show that the inclusion of the aerodynamic stiffness is important to get accurate predictions of the seal stability, specially at conditions for which the mechanical frequency is such that $St_m \approx 1$. Seals operating with small clearances and large pressure ratios are particularly affected by this effect.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The seal flutter problem has been revisited in this paper with the aim of providing an improved semi-analytical model for its prediction. First, a physical description of the flutter phenomenon has been provided from a frame of reference that rotates with the vibration travelling wave. From this perspective

the vibration appears as a stationary wave and the flow in the cavity appears steady, travelling at a mean speed equal to the vibration wave but in opposite direction (see right-hand side of Figure 2). The flow behavior can then be characterized in terms of its mean Mach number, which is equivalent to the Strouhal number when the air frame of reference is used instead. Abbott's criteria [4] were then physically explained using the frame of reference rotating with the travelling vibration wave.

It was also shown that during the seal vibration an aerodynamic stiffness term arises due to the pressure response in the seal cavities. For the idealized *zero-leakage* case, the aerodynamic stiffness was shown to be negative for $St < 1$ and positive for $St > 1$. The introduction of the leakage flow, featured in labyrinth seals, leads to an aerodynamic damping term, which is a function of the frequency of vibration. As a result, the aerodynamic stiffness can influence the seal stability, as it affects the frequency of vibration. It was shown that its influence tends to be largest when the mechanical frequency is close to the acoustic frequency ($St_m \approx 1$) and is particularly important at *small* seal clearance conditions. The aerodynamic stiffness effect also means a careful use of the prescribed vibration method in CFD analyses is required, as it can lead to incorrect aerodynamic damping predictions when the stiffness term is important.

Moreover, for multiple cavity seals it was shown that the leakage flow over the fin tip is, in general, influenced by the pressure responses in the upstream and downstream cavities, leading to a coupling across the cavities. The analytical method can be extended to include this effect leading to a set of coupled, algebraic equations which can be represented by a banded matrix. The inclusion of the cross-cavity coupling effect was shown to significantly improve the predictions when compared to CFD and experimental results.

The inclusion of both the aerodynamic stiffness and cross-cavity coupling effects overall improve the predictions from the flutter model, making them comparable to CFD, and despite the added complexity in the method, the increased computation cost is negligible compared to more expensive methods such as CFD.

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7. APPENDIX A: Single-Cavity, Non-rotating Seal

Reference [8] provides the derivation of the unsteady pressure response of the flow within a single-cavity, non-rotating seal during vibration. The analysis is performed in the air frame of reference, where the flow conservation equations

are applied. This section provides a similar derivation, but it is done in the frame of reference of the vibration travelling wave, as shown on the right-hand side of Figure 2. The advantage of using this frame of reference is that the flow can be treated as steady. When the flow is viewed from this perspective, the flow is somewhat similar to that in a convergent-divergent nozzle. It will be shown that equivalent equations as those reported in [8] are obtained with this approach.

A linear version of the equations is presented here and thus small variations in the flow properties are assumed. For simplicity, it is assumed that the flow is isentropic, and the seal cavity mean (i.e. steady) temperature is constant throughout.

Figure 14 shows the control volume, from both the seal axis and cross-section views. The control volume is bounded by stations 1 and 2 in the circumferential direction, as shown in the figure. Note that the mean flow velocity in the cavity is not zero and equal to $\bar{v}_c = \omega_s R_c$ due to the frame of reference used. Since the flow is treated as *steady-state*, the transient terms in the mass and mass-momentum equations vanish.

FIGURE 14: CONTROL VOLUME USED FOR ANALYSIS

The mass conservation equation for the steady flow can be written as:

$$\dot{m}_2 + \dot{m}_{fe} = \dot{m}_1 + \dot{m}_{fi} \quad (A1)$$

The upstream fin tip mass flow is given by:

$$\dot{m}_{fi} = \frac{p_{T,i} H_i \delta z Q_i}{\sqrt{T_{T,i}}} \quad (A2)$$

Where Q is the non-dimensional mass flow given by:

$$Q = \frac{\dot{m} \sqrt{T_T}}{A \cdot p_T} \quad (A3)$$

For the upstream fin, the inlet pressure and temperatures, $p_{T,i}$ and $T_{T,i}$, are assumed constant. Equation A2 can be linearized as follows:

$$\dot{m}_{fi} = \bar{m}_f \frac{\delta z}{2\pi R_c} + \bar{m}_f \frac{\Delta H_i}{\bar{H}_i} \frac{\delta z}{2\pi R_c} + \bar{m}_f \frac{\Delta Q_i}{\bar{Q}_i} \frac{\delta z}{2\pi R_c} \quad (A4)$$

Where $\bar{m}_f = \frac{p_{T,i} 2\pi R_c \bar{H}_i \bar{Q}_i}{\sqrt{T_{T,i}}}$ and $\bar{H}_i = \frac{\Delta H_i}{\bar{H}_i}$. The non-dimensional mass flow Q_i is a function of the fin tip pressure ratio¹ and can be linearized as follows:

$$\Delta Q_i = \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial PR_i} \Delta PR_i \quad (A5)$$

¹ For a PR leading to an isentropic Mach number $M > 1$, the flow is choked and Q becomes constant against PR and equal to the choked flow Q_{choke} . Thus, at the choked flow condition: $\frac{\partial Q}{\partial PR} = 0$.

Where $PR_i = \frac{p_{T,i}}{p_c}$. Therefore:

$$\Delta Q_i = -Q_i' \overline{PR}_i \frac{\Delta p_c}{\bar{p}_c} \quad (\text{A6})$$

Where $Q_i' = \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial PR_i}$ is evaluated at the pressure ratio \overline{PR}_i .

Note that: $\tilde{p}_c = \frac{\Delta p_c}{\bar{p}_c}$. Therefore equation A4 becomes:

$$\dot{m}_i = \bar{m}_f \frac{\delta z}{2\pi R_c} \left(1 + \tilde{H}_i - \frac{Q_i'}{\bar{Q}_i} \overline{PR}_i \tilde{p}_c \right) \quad (\text{A7})$$

The downstream fin tip mass flow can be assessed in a similar manner. Linearizing equation A2 for the downstream fin leads to:

$$\dot{m}_{fe} = \bar{m}_f \frac{\delta z}{2\pi R_c} + \bar{m}_f \frac{\Delta H_e}{\bar{H}_e} \frac{\delta z}{2\pi R_c} + \bar{m}_f \frac{\Delta Q_e}{\bar{Q}_e} \frac{\delta z}{2\pi R_c} + \bar{m}_f \frac{\Delta p_c}{\bar{p}_c} \frac{\delta z}{2\pi R_c} + \bar{m}_f \frac{\Delta T_c}{2\bar{T}_c} \frac{\delta z}{2\pi R_c} \quad (\text{A8})$$

Reference [8] assumes $\Delta T_c = 0$. Here, instead it is assumed that temperature variations follow an isentropic process. Linearizing the isentropic relationship for temperature:

$$\frac{T_c}{\bar{T}_c} = \frac{p_c}{\bar{p}_c}^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}} \quad (\text{A9})$$

Leads to:

$$\frac{\Delta T_c}{\bar{T}_c} = \frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma} \frac{\Delta p_c}{\bar{p}_c} \quad (\text{A10})$$

The downstream fin ΔQ_e is given by:

$$\Delta Q_e = Q_e' \overline{PR}_e \frac{\Delta p_c}{\bar{p}_c} \quad (\text{A11})$$

Since the downstream (exit) pressure is assumed to be constant. Therefore, equation A8 becomes:

$$\dot{m}_{fe} = \bar{m}_f \frac{\delta z}{2\pi R_c} \left[1 + \tilde{H}_e + \left(\frac{\gamma+1}{2\gamma} + \frac{Q_e'}{\bar{Q}_e} \overline{PR}_e \right) \tilde{p}_c \right] \quad (\text{A12})$$

And the local net flow rate into the seal cavity is:

$$\dot{m}_{fi} - \dot{m}_{fe} = \bar{m}_f \frac{\delta z}{2\pi R_c} [\tilde{H}_i - \tilde{H}_e - h\tilde{p}_c] \quad (\text{A13})$$

Where h is a constant that depends on both upstream and downstream mean fin tip pressure ratios, defined as:

$$h = \frac{\gamma+1}{2\gamma} + \frac{Q_i'}{\bar{Q}_i} \overline{PR}_i + \frac{Q_e'}{\bar{Q}_e} \overline{PR}_e \quad (\text{A14})$$

The mass flow rates in the circumferential direction, \dot{m}_1 and \dot{m}_2 , are now considered. Since $\dot{m} = \rho_c v_c A_\theta$, then across a small interval δz :

$$\dot{m}_2 - \dot{m}_1 = \bar{\rho}_c \bar{v}_c \bar{A}_\theta \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{p}_c}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{\bar{v}} \frac{\partial v_c}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial \tilde{A}_\theta}{\partial z} \right) \delta z \quad (\text{A15})$$

Where $\bar{v}_c = \omega_s R_c$ is the mean velocity set by the speed of the vibration travelling wave, $A_\theta = L \cdot s$ and $\bar{m}_\theta = \bar{\rho}_c \bar{v}_c \bar{A}_\theta$ is the mean mass flow rate in the θ direction. Since the flow is assumed to be isentropic, the pressure and density variations are related by:

$$\delta p_c = \bar{a}_c^2 \delta \rho_c \quad (\text{A16})$$

And the mean values are related by:

$$\bar{p}_c = \frac{\bar{a}_c^2}{\gamma} \bar{\rho}_c \quad (\text{A17})$$

And therefore, equation A14 can be written as:

$$\dot{m}_2 - \dot{m}_1 = \bar{m}_\theta \left(\frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}_c}{\partial \bar{z}} + \frac{1}{\gamma St} \frac{\partial \tilde{v}_c}{\partial \bar{z}} + \frac{\partial \tilde{A}_\theta}{\partial \bar{z}} \right) \frac{R_c}{ND} \delta \bar{z} \quad (\text{A18})$$

Where:

$$St = \frac{\omega}{\omega_{ac}} = \frac{\omega R_c}{\bar{a}_c ND}, \quad \tilde{v}_c = \gamma \frac{\Delta v_c}{\bar{a}_c} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{z} = ND \cdot \theta = \frac{z}{R_c} ND \quad (\text{A19})$$

Substituting A13 and A18 into equation A1 leads to:

$$\frac{\bar{m}_\theta}{\bar{m}_f} \left(\frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}_c}{\partial \bar{z}} + \frac{1}{\gamma St} \frac{\partial \tilde{v}_c}{\partial \bar{z}} + \frac{\partial \tilde{A}_\theta}{\partial \bar{z}} \right) = (\tilde{H}_i - \tilde{H}_e - h\tilde{p}_c) \frac{1}{2\pi ND} \quad (\text{A20})$$

Define $\Omega = \frac{\bar{p}_c \bar{v}_c}{\bar{m}_f \bar{a}_c^2} \omega$ and equation A20 becomes:

$$\Omega \left(\gamma \frac{\partial \tilde{A}_\theta}{\partial \bar{z}} + \frac{\partial \tilde{p}_c}{\partial \bar{z}} + \frac{1}{St} \frac{\partial \tilde{v}_c}{\partial \bar{z}} \right) = \tilde{H}_i - \tilde{H}_e - h\tilde{p}_c \quad (\text{A21})$$

Now consider the steady-state form of the mass-momentum equation in the circumferential direction. For the control volume in Figure 14, it can be written as:

$$(p_{c,1} - p_{c,2})A_\theta = \dot{m}_2 v_{c,2} - \dot{m}_1 v_{c,1} + (\dot{m}_{fe} - \dot{m}_{fi})\bar{v}_c \quad (\text{A22})$$

The last term in equation A22 represents the momentum flux in the circumferential direction due to the fin tip leakage flow. Note that the fin tip leakage flow is assumed to have only axial velocity component in the air frame of reference but since the frame of reference used for the analysis rotates relative to the mean air flow, the leakage flow velocity is observed to have a tangential component given by $\bar{v}_c = \omega_s R_c$.

Linearizing the term $\dot{m}_2 v_{c,2} - \dot{m}_1 v_{c,1}$ in A22 leads to:

$$\dot{m}_2 v_{c,2} - \dot{m}_1 v_{c,1} = \bar{m}_\theta (\Delta v_{c,2} - \Delta v_{c,1}) + \bar{v}_c (\dot{m}_2 - \dot{m}_1) \quad (\text{A23})$$

The continuity equation A1 can be written as: $\dot{m}_2 - \dot{m}_1 = -(\dot{m}_{fe} - \dot{m}_{fi})$ and therefore equation A23 reduces to:

$$(p_{c,1} - p_{c,2})A_\theta = \bar{m}_\theta (\Delta v_{c,2} - \Delta v_{c,1}) \quad (\text{A24})$$

Or in differential form:

$$\frac{\partial p_c}{\partial z} A_\theta = \bar{m}_\theta \frac{\partial v_c}{\partial z} \quad (\text{A25})$$

Equation A25 can be written in non-dimensional form as:

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{p}_c}{\partial \bar{z}} = -St \frac{\partial \tilde{v}_c}{\partial \bar{z}} \quad (\text{A26})$$

Given a vibration mode, equations A21 and A26 can be used to resolve for the variables \tilde{v}_c and \tilde{p}_c . Note that the vibration mode (defined by a nodal diameter, an amplitude and a frequency) fully determine the source terms \tilde{A}_θ , \tilde{H}_i and \tilde{H}_e :

$$\tilde{A}_\theta = \tilde{A}_\theta e^{i\bar{z}}, \quad \tilde{H}_i = \tilde{H}_{o,i} e^{i\bar{z}} \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{H}_e = \tilde{H}_{o,e} e^{i\bar{z}} \quad (\text{A27})$$

Equations A21 and A26 accept solutions of the form:

$$\tilde{v}_c = \hat{v}_o e^{i\bar{z}} \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{p}_c = \hat{p}_o e^{i\bar{z}} \quad (\text{A28})$$

From equation A26: $\hat{v}_o = -\frac{\tilde{p}_o}{St}$ (A29)

Substituting equations A27, A28 and A29 into A21 leads to:

$$Re[\tilde{p}_o] = c\tilde{p} = \frac{h(\bar{H}_{o,i} - \bar{H}_{o,e}) - \gamma\bar{A}_o\Omega^2\left(1 - \frac{1}{St^2}\right)}{h^2 + \Omega^2\left(1 - \frac{1}{St^2}\right)^2} \quad (A30)$$

$$Im[\tilde{p}_o] = -s\tilde{p} = -\frac{\Omega[\gamma\bar{A}_oh + (\bar{H}_{o,i} - \bar{H}_{o,e})\left(1 - \frac{1}{St^2}\right)]}{h^2 + \Omega^2\left(1 - \frac{1}{St^2}\right)^2} \quad (A31)$$

Where: $\Omega = \frac{\bar{p}_c\bar{V}_c}{\bar{m}_f\bar{a}_c^2}\omega$ and $St = \frac{\omega}{\omega_{ac}}$ (A32)

And h is defined by equation A14. Equations A30 and A31 can be written in a more useful non-dimensional form:

$$Re[\hat{p}_o] = c\tilde{p} = \frac{h\varepsilon - \varphi^2 St_m^2 \tilde{\omega}^2 \kappa \left(1 - \frac{1}{St_m^2 \tilde{\omega}^2}\right)}{h^2 + \varphi^2 St_m^2 \tilde{\omega}^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{St_m^2 \tilde{\omega}^2}\right)^2} \quad (A33)$$

$$Im[\hat{p}_o] = -s\tilde{p} = -\frac{\varphi St_m \tilde{\omega} \left[h\kappa + \varepsilon \left(1 - \frac{1}{St_m^2 \tilde{\omega}^2}\right) \right]}{h^2 + \varphi^2 St_m^2 \tilde{\omega}^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{St_m^2 \tilde{\omega}^2}\right)^2} \quad (A34)$$

With the following non-dimensional definitions:

$$\varepsilon = \bar{H}_{o,i} - \bar{H}_{o,e}, \quad \kappa = \gamma\bar{A}_o, \quad \varphi = \frac{\bar{p}_c\bar{V}_c}{\bar{m}_f\bar{a}_c^2}\omega_{ac}, \quad \tilde{\omega} = \frac{\omega}{\omega_m}, \quad St_m = \frac{\omega_m}{\omega_{ac}} \quad (A35)$$

Note that a distinction between the vibration frequency (St) and the mechanical frequency (St_m) has been made following the discussion in section 3.1. Moreover, equations A33 and A34 have been written in terms of $\varphi St_m \tilde{\omega}$, instead of Ω . This is because it is convenient to explicitly present the dependencies of the pressure coefficients in terms of St_m , and $\tilde{\omega}$. Trends obtained from equations A33 and A34 are presented in section 4.1.

Using the cavity dimensions shown in Figure 14 and assuming uniform mean clearances ($\bar{H}_i = \bar{H}_e$) leads to:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\alpha_o L}{\bar{H}}, \quad \kappa = \gamma \frac{r\alpha_o}{s} \quad (A36)$$

The fully sealed cavity (zero-leakage flow) case described in section 2.1 can be represented by setting $\Omega \rightarrow \infty$ in equations A30 and A31 leading to:

$$\frac{\Delta p_o}{\bar{p}_c} = \gamma \frac{St^2}{(1-St^2)} \frac{\Delta A_o}{\bar{A}_\theta} \quad (A37)$$

Finally note that from equation A14, $h \geq \frac{\gamma+1}{2\gamma}$. And assuming $\gamma = 1.4$, then $h \geq 0.857$. The simplified analysis presented in section 2.2 assumed that the leakage flow is only proportional to the fin clearance. While this is not physically possible, this situation can be modelled by imposing $h = 0$ in equations A33 and A34. This leads to:

$$Re[\hat{p}_o] = c\tilde{p} = \gamma \frac{St^2}{(1-St^2)} \frac{\Delta A_o}{\bar{A}_\theta} \quad (A38)$$

$$Im[\hat{p}_o] = -s\tilde{p} = \frac{\varepsilon St^2}{\Omega(1-St^2)} \quad (A39)$$

Where ε represents the amplitude of the net leakage flow, $\delta\dot{m}$, described in section 2.2.

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